

APPENDIX 1: Interview Guide

Tradbank Interview Questions, Agile Team Members/Programme and Project Managers/DevOps Managers/Unit CIOs

Work Background:

1. Please tell me about your background and how you came to be in this position.
2. What is your role at Tradbank? What do you do in a typical workday?
3. What is your job level in Tradbank?
4. How many years of experience do you have in Waterfall projects?
5. How many years of experience do you have in Agile projects?

Agile Journey Experience:

6. Tell me about the history of Agile at Tradbank
7. How is the Agile transformation progressing at Tradbank?
8. How are the business and IT leaders supporting Agile?
9. What changes were made in the IT environment to support Agile?
10. What changes were made in the business environment to support Agile?
11. What have been the key challenges/benefits in transitioning to Agile?

Relationship Experiences with Governance and Compliance Units:

12. How responsive are your governance and compliance units in supporting Agile?
Probe experience with specific units (x=PMO, Internal Audits, Risk)
13. 1. What changes were made to X's processes to support the Agile practices?
Please elaborate.
13. 2. How involved are X unit's representatives in your Agile projects? Examples.
13. 3. How do you think the relationship with X unit is going overall? Please describe.

Outcomes:

14. How do you cope with these transformation challenges? Please elaborate.
15. Have you noticed any changes to team/IT unit/organisational performance since the Agile transformation began? Examples.
16. How successful has the Agile transformation been? Examples.
17. Any other comments?
18. Who else do you think I should talk to?

Note 1: Some questions were adapted to suit the participant's role.

Note 2: Some interviews involved fewer questions to accommodate the participant's role and time limitations.

Note 3: Some questions were explored further using appropriate probes.